

CLEWISE: An Inventory-Consistent Framework for NDC and LTS

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CLEWISE Framework

NDCs and LTSs are written and tracked in the language of national greenhouse gas inventories. They report progress by IPCC sector [1] and by gas [2], following the accounting rules set out in the Enhanced Transparency Framework [3]. Yet most quantitative mitigation models are usually focused on energy, and don't properly account for land use, industrial processes, or waste.

Nexus frameworks in the Climate Land Energy Water tradition work to integrate sectors, but recent reviews point to a persistent gap: no existing implementation systematically treats all four IPCC inventory sectors as endogenous, optimizable parts of one model. Most omit industrial processes or waste altogether, and few calibrate their BAU scenario against historical inventory totals, leaving their results disconnected from official national reporting.

To close this gap we developed CLEWISE (Climate Land Energy Waste Industry for all IPCC Sector Emissions), an open source framework that extends the CLEWs family of models to represent the Energy, AFOLU, IPPU, and Waste sectors within a single optimization framework. It is the first inventory consistent CLEWs/OSeMOSYS extension that spans Energy, AFOLU, IPPU, and Waste together, with documented, reusable templates that let a modelling team adapt the framework to a new country without rebuilding it from scratch. It builds on OSeMOSYS, a modelling system valued for its transparency [4], its relatively light data requirements [5], and its flexibility to adapt to different national contexts [6]. These qualities have made the broader CLEWs family a common choice for national energy and resource planning [7].

Building on this foundation, the framework adds three modular templates for AFOLU, IPPU, and Waste, that countries populate with their own activity data and emission factors. It also includes an emissions accounting layer that maps model activity into IPCC inventory categories and gases, so model outputs stay consistent with a country's own greenhouse gas inventory. Countries can use CLEWISE to draft or update their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) and Long Term Strategies (LTS), working from a framework built to be both complete and methodologically sound.

Framework Architecture

CLEWISE is implemented as a linear, least-cost optimization model using the open-source OSeMOSYS formulation. The model minimizes the discounted sum of investment, operation and maintenance, and fuel costs subject to constraints on energy balance, capacity expansion and retirement, resource availability. On top of the standard OSeMOSYS structure, CLEWISE defines additional commodities and activity variables for AFOLU, IPPU and waste, and introduces an emissions accounting layer that converts activity levels into emissions by IPCC category and gas. Model inputs (activity data, emission factors, technology parameters) are stored in open text formats (CSV/Excel) and version-controlled in a public Git repository. The main modules in CLEWISE are:

Energy and transport module

This module follows standard OSeMOSYS practice, covering supply technologies (hydropower, geothermal, wind, solar, biomass, fossil-fired plants), transformation processes (refineries, power plants, combined heat and power), and end-use demand in transport, industry, and buildings. Transport demand is split into modal segments such as private vehicles, buses, and freight, each with technology options ranging from internal combustion engines to electric vehicles and alternative fuels. Combustion emissions are calculated from fuel flows using emission factors consistent with inventory practice.

Figure 1. Energy and Transport module diagram

AFOLU module.

The agriculture component covers the two dominant livestock-related sources, enteric fermentation and manure management, driven by livestock populations, herd composition, and pastureland, plus direct and indirect emissions from managed soils linked to fertilizer use and crop area. The land-use, land-use-change, and forestry component groups land into aggregate classes (forest, cropland, grassland, settlements, and other land) and tracks transitions between them through transition matrices that capture deforestation, afforestation, and reforestation. Emissions and removals come from changes in land area combined with per-hectare carbon stock change factors.

Figure 2. AFOLU module diagram.

Note: Forest and crop types can be adjusted by country

Waste module

This module represents solid waste and wastewater from generation through treatment and final disposal, following IPCC waste categories. The model tracks municipal solid waste collection, recycling, composting, incineration, and landfilling, including gas generation and recovery, with flaring and electricity generation routes. Wastewater is represented through generation volumes, treatment-level choices, and associated activity emissions.

Figure 3. Waste module diagram.

IPPU module

This module captures emissions that occur independently of fuel combustion, including cement and lime production. Where data allows, the module extends to selected industrial chemicals and metals using simplified activity-based formulations, and to fluorinated gases (HFCs in refrigeration and air conditioning) by linking gas consumption or equipment activity to emission or leakage factors.

Figure 4. IPPU module diagram.

Main contributions

Aligning model structure with inventory structure builds a direct methodological bridge between two communities that often work in isolation: inventory compilers and integrated-assessment modelers. Because CLEWISE expresses every activity in inventory-recognizable terms, inventory teams can engage with model assumptions and results using a known classification system, which raises transparency and trust in scenario outputs. It also lets planning and finance ministries read emissions, energy-intensity, and investment indicators side by side with the official statistics they already track.

CLEWISE also moves scenario-building beyond pure cost optimization. Modelers can encode the way policy works by adding their technology adoption floors and ceilings, phase-out dates, build-rate limits, sectoral caps tied to NDC or LTS targets to reflect real policy design.

Beyond its technical contribution, CLEWISE functions as an institutional interface. Its open-source, version-controlled structure and documented calibration routine give inventory compilers, sectoral planners, modelers, and finance officials a shared analytical reference point, supporting the iterative updates that NDC and LTS processes demand.

References

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